

Hexa-co-ordinated Complexes of Nickel(II) Oxalate with Amines

Gopal Narain

Hexa-co-ordinated complexes of nickel(II) oxalate with ammonia, ethylenediamine, and propylenediamine have been prepared. Conductance and M. W. measurements in nitrobenzene indicate the complexes to be nonelectrolytes. The visible absorption spectrophotometric measurements exhibit four absorption bands in the vicinity of 350, 560, 625, and 625 m μ . Attempts have been made to discuss the *d-d* spectrum of nickel in this particular case.

Very little work appears to have been done on organic salts of nickel to study the relation between the colour and stereochemistry of the complexes. The existence of the complexes in nickel oxalate-ethylenediamine solution has been reported¹ and the nature of the anion is found to be a contributing factor towards the stability of the complexes². The present communication deals with the synthesis, preliminary investigations, and visible absorption measurements in order to study the electronic transitions taking place inside the nickel atom and to correlate these with the position of the absorption maximum.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mono-oxalato-tetrakis (amine)nickel (II).—Nickel (II) oxalate (500 g.) was placed in a calcium chloride tube, fitted with a cotton-wool plug at the bottom. The tube was attached to the neck of a flask containing excess of amine and was left overnight. The tube was taken out in the morning and dried first over CaCl₂ and then over P₂O₅. The complex is greenish blue in colour and soluble in nitrobenzene. (Found: Ni, 27.06; N, 26.96; NH₃, 31.38; M.W., 196. C₂H₁₂O₄N₄.Ni requires Ni, 27.34; N, 26.08; NH₃, 31.67%; M.W., 214.7). Conductance=0.23 mho.

Mono-oxalato-bis (ethylenediamine) nickel(II).—Nickel (II) oxalate (500 mg.) was shaken in acetone with calculated quantity of amine for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was left overnight, filtered, and dried over P₂O₅. The complex is blue in colour and soluble in nitrobenzene. (Found: Ni, 21.88; N, 20.89; en, 45.20; M.W., 251. C₈H₁₆O₄N₄.Ni requires Ni, 22.01; N, 21.00; en, 45.00%; M.W., 266.7). Conductance=0.18 mho.

Mono-oxalato-bis (propylenediamine)nickel(II) was prepared similarly as the preceding complex. The complex is blue in colour and soluble in nitrobenzene. (Found: Ni, 19.78; N, 19.20; pn, 50.40; M.W., 278. C₈H₁₆O₄N₄.Ni requires Ni, 19.92; N, 19.00; pn, 50.23%; M.W., 294.7). Conductance=0.34 mho.

1. Walters and Dewitt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1333.
2. Moeller, "Inorganic Chemistry", 1st Indian printing, p. 237, 1962.

Determinations of the base and molecular weight were made by the methods as outlined by the author³.

Visible Absorption Spectra.—Spectra were recorded on a Unicam S.P. 500 spectrophotometer in nitrobenzene. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

[Ni(C ₂ O ₄)(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺ .		[Ni(C ₂ O ₄)(en) ₂] ²⁺ .		[Ni(C ₂ O ₄)(pn) ₂] ²⁺ .	
$\lambda_{\max}$.	Frequency.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Frequency.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Frequency.
350 m μ	28600 cm ⁻¹	340 m μ	29400 cm ⁻¹	345 m μ	29000 cm ⁻¹
550	18700	550	18000	550	18700
800	12500	820	12200	800	12500
925	10800	915	10930	920	10800

The results of analysis show the molecular formulas to be Ni(C₂O₄)(ax)₄ and Ni(C₂O₄)(am)_n, where 'am' represents any amine used. Measurements of conductance in nitrobenzene indicate a value less than 1, showing that the complexes behave as non-electrolytes⁴. Molecular weight measurements confirm this and hence it is suggested that oxalate ions, besides neutralising the charge of the metal, are also co-ordinated. The formulas of the complexes are thus to be written as [Ni(C₂O₄)(am)₄]⁰ and [Ni(C₂O₄)(am)_n]²⁺.

Ballhausen⁵ has shown that at least 3 or 4 transitions are to be expected for octahedral complexes. Their positions are theoretically shown to be: $\nu_1 = 10Dq$; $\nu_2 = 9/5 (10Dq)$; $\nu_3 = 17000 + 6/5 (10Dq)$.

The above complexes also show four bands. Moreover, as demonstrated by Fernelius⁶, the ratio ν_3/ν_1 is 1.82 for all octahedral complexes, irrespective of the ligands used for co-ordination. The 925 m μ band in this case is considered to be ν_1 band and the position of other bands is then calculated by the above equation and it is thus found that ν_3/ν_1 is 1.82 in this case, and that there is a fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values. The bands are proposed to correspond to the following transitions (Table II).

TABLE II

Frequency.	Wave length.	Transition.
$\nu_1(10800 \text{ cm}^{-1})$	925 m μ	$3A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$
$\nu_2(12500 \text{ cm}^{-1})$	800	$3A_{1g} \rightarrow 1E_g$
$\nu_3(18700 \text{ cm}^{-1})$	550	$3A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$
$\nu_4(28600 \text{ cm}^{-1})$	350	$3A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$

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3. Under publication in *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*

4. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1714.

5. *Dan. Mat.fys. Medel.*, 1954, 29, No. 4.

6. *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1951, 38, 192.